

	1296	1301	1303	1307	1316	1334	1428
CP077224.1:66337-67893 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain FDAARGOS 1454	G	A	T	C	T	T	C
CP077224.1:210685-212241 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain FDAARGOS 1454	G	A	T	C	T	T	C
CP077224.1:1358567-1360123 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain FDAARGOS 1454	G	A	T	C	T	T	C
CP077224.1:1619370-1620926 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain FDAARGOS 1454	G	A	T	C	T	T	C
CP012648.1:4168-5724 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain KCOM 1506	A	G	T	T	C	C	C
CP012648.1:665098-666654 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain KCOM 1506	A	G	T	T	C	C	C
CP012648.1:814030-815586 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain KCOM 1506	A	G	T	T	C	C	C
CP012648.1:1081173-1082729 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain KCOM 1506	A	A	T	C	T	T	C
CP012648.1:2281631-2283187 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain KCOM 1506	A	G	T	T	C	C	C
LR134291.1:660986-662542 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain NCTC7868	A	G	T	T	C	T	C
LR134291.1:1768394-1769950 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain NCTC7868	A	G	T	T	C	T	C
LR134291.1:2020402-2021958 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain NCTC7868	A	G	T	T	C	T	C
LR134291.1:2176843-2178399 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain NCTC7868	A	A	A	T	C	C	T
LR594041.1:645341-646897 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain NCTC9124	A	G	T	T	C	T	T
LR594041.1:1799885-1801441 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain NCTC9124	A	A	A	T	C	C	T
LR594041.1:2059532-2061088 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain NCTC9124	A	A	A	T	C	C	T
LR594041.1:2204098-2205654 <i>S.gordonii</i> strain NCTC9124	A	G	T	T	C	C	C

Figure S1. Intra-species Parsim-info variable sites in the 16S rRNA gene from *S. gordonii*. According to Chakravorty et al (2007), the nine variable regions of 16S rRNA gene spanned nucleotides 69-99, 137-242, 433-497, 576-682, 822-879, 986-1043, 1117-1173, 1243-1294, and 1435-1465 for V1 to V9 respectively.

	61	63	377	1312	1338	1427	1430	1431	1441	1442
NC 013853.1:16691-18236 <i>S.mitis</i> B6	T	C	A	T	C	A	G	A	C	T
NC 013853.1:173665-175210 <i>S.mitis</i> B6	T	C	A	T	C	A	G	A	C	T
NC 013853.1:238747-240292 <i>S.mitis</i> B6	T	C	A	T	C	A	G	A	C	T
NC 013853.1:451360-452905 <i>S.mitis</i> B6	T	C	A	T	C	A	G	A	C	T
CP012646.1:169013-170567 <i>S.mitis</i> strain KCOM 1350	T	C	G	T	A	G	G	A	C	T
CP012646.1:215810-217355 <i>S.mitis</i> strain KCOM 1350	T	C	G	T	C	A	A	G	C	T
CP012646.1:363679-365224 <i>S.mitis</i> strain KCOM 1350	T	C	G	T	C	A	A	G	C	T
CP014326.1:192413-193958 <i>S.mitis</i> strain SVGS 061	T	C	A	C	A	A	A	G	T	C
CP014326.1:15147-16692 <i>S.mitis</i> strain SVGS 061	T	C	A	C	A	A	A	G	T	C
CP014326.1:252667-254212 <i>S.mitis</i> strain SVGS 061	T	C	A	C	A	A	A	G	T	C
CP014326.1:430145-431690 <i>S.mitis</i> strain SVGS 061	T	C	A	C	A	A	A	G	T	C
CP028414.1:15255-16801 <i>S.mitis</i> NCTC 12261	A	A	A	T	C	G	G	A	C	T
CP028414.1:170503-172049 <i>S.mitis</i> NCTC 12261	A	A	A	T	C	G	G	A	C	T
CP028414.1:214057-215603 <i>S.mitis</i> NCTC 12261	A	A	A	T	C	G	G	A	C	T
CP028414.1:374312-375857 <i>S.mitis</i> NCTC 12261	A	A	A	T	C	G	G	A	C	T

Figure S2. Intra-species Parsim-info variable sites in the 16S rRNA gene from *S. mitis*. According to Chakravorty et al (2007), the nine variable regions of 16S rRNA gene spanned nucleotides 69-99, 137-242, 433-497, 576-682, 822-879, 986-1043, 1117-1173, 1243-1294, and 1435-1465 for V1 to V9 respectively.

	490	654	1236	1256	1296	1301	1312	1315	1316	1318	1319	1321	1330	1332	1335	1338	1427	1428	1429	1432	1433	1440	1443	1444
LR134336.1:14791-16339 S.oralis strain NCTC 11427	A	G	T	T	A	A	T	G	T	A	A	G	C	T	A	C	G	C	T	G	T	A	A	A
LR134336.1:133092-134640 S.oralis strain NCTC 11427	A	G	T	T	A	A	T	G	T	A	A	G	C	T	A	C	G	C	T	G	T	A	A	A
LR134336.1:174955-176503 S.oralis strain NCTC 11427	A	G	T	T	A	A	T	G	T	A	A	G	C	T	A	C	G	C	T	G	T	A	A	A
LR134336.1:1524583-1526131 S.oralis strain NCTC 11427	A	G	T	T	A	A	T	G	T	A	A	G	C	T	A	C	G	C	T	G	T	A	A	A
CP079724.1:14357-15903 S.oralis strain 34	A	G	T	T	A	T	T	G	C	A	A	G	C	T	A	C	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP079724.1:138141-139687 S.oralis strain 34	A	G	T	T	A	T	T	G	C	A	A	G	C	T	A	C	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP079724.1:179043-180589 S.oralis strain 34	A	G	T	T	A	T	T	G	C	A	A	G	C	T	A	C	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP079724.1:395600-397146 S.oralis strain 34	A	G	T	T	A	T	T	G	C	A	A	G	C	T	A	C	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP065706.1:195212-196758 S.oralis strain FDAARGOS 886	G	A	C	C	G	A	C	A	C	G	T	A	T	A	G	A	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP065706.1:342932-344478 S.oralis strain FDAARGOS 886	G	A	C	C	G	A	C	A	C	G	T	A	T	A	G	A	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP065706.1:385505-387051 S.oralis strain FDAARGOS 886	G	A	C	C	G	A	C	A	C	G	T	A	T	A	G	A	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP065706.1:1694773-1696319 S.oralis strain FDAARGOS 886	G	A	C	C	G	A	C	A	C	G	T	A	T	A	G	A	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP034442.1:1030705-1032251 S.oralis strain F0392	G	G	C	C	G	A	C	A	C	G	T	A	T	A	G	A	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP034442.1:1462326-1463872 S.oralis strain F0392	G	G	C	C	G	A	C	A	C	G	T	A	T	A	G	A	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP034442.1:1598728-1600274 S.oralis strain F0392	G	G	C	C	G	A	C	A	C	G	T	A	T	A	G	A	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C
CP034442.1:1671919-1673465 S.oralis strain F0392	G	G	C	C	G	A	C	A	C	G	T	A	T	A	G	A	A	G	A	A	A	T	T	C

Figure S3. Intra-species Parsim-info variable sites in the 16S rRNA gene from *S. oralis*. According to Chakravorty et al (2007), the nine variable regions of 16S rRNA gene spanned nucleotides 69-99, 137-242, 433-497, 576-682, 822-879, 986-1043, 1117-1173, 1243-1294, and 1435-1465 for V1 to V9 respectively.

	376	489	504	505	518	1333
CP046355.1:185623-187168 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain 475	G	G	C	G	T	T
CP046355.1:247645-249190 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain 475	G	G	C	G	T	T
CP046355.1:338998-340543 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain 475	G	G	C	G	T	C
CP046355.1:2166294-2167839 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain 475	G	G	C	G	T	T
AP018936.1:15152-16697 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain NU83127	A	G	C	G	T	T
AP018936.1:1832917-1834462 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain NU83127	A	G	C	G	C	T
AP018936.1:1931573-1933118 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain NU83127	A	G	C	G	C	T
AP018936.1:1994836-1996381 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain NU83127	A	G	C	G	C	T
LN831051.1:480477-482022 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain NCTC7465	A	A	T	C	T	T
LN831051.1:679934-681479 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain NCTC7465	A	A	T	C	T	T
LN831051.1:742022-743567 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain NCTC7465	A	A	T	C	T	T
LN831051.1:833947-835492 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain NCTC7465	A	A	T	C	T	T
CP053210.1:27613-29158 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain 6A-10	A	A	C	G	T	C
CP053210.1:1876218-1877763 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain 6A-10	A	A	C	G	T	C
CP053210.1:1969562-1971107 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain 6A-10	A	A	C	G	T	C
CP053210.1:2036937-2038482 <i>S.pneumoniae</i> strain 6A-10	A	A	C	G	T	C

Figure S4. Intra-species Parsim-info variable sites in the 16S rRNA gene from *S. pneumoniae*. According to Chakravorty et al (2007), the nine variable regions of 16S rRNA gene spanned nucleotides 69-99, 137-242, 433-497, 576-682, 822-879, 986-1043, 1117-1173, 1243-1294, and 1435-1465 for V1 to V9 respectively.